

Education, Ideology and the National Education Policy (NEP 2020): A Critical Analysis

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Abstract:

This research paper critically examines the relationship between education, ideology, and the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020). It argues that education is not merely a neutral process of knowledge transmission but a powerful socio-political institution that shapes beliefs, values, and social consciousness. The paper highlights how education often functions as an ideological tool that sustains existing power structures.

The study traces the historical evolution of the Indian education system emphasizing how inequalities based on caste, class, and gender have continued in different forms from the exclusive Gurukul system to colonial reforms and post-independence democratization. It further explores the impact of globalization and neoliberal policies, which have transformed education into a market-driven commodity, increasing privatization and limiting access for marginalized groups.

The paper critically evaluates NEP 2020, acknowledging its vision for flexibility, multidisciplinary learning, and modernization. However, it raises concerns regarding centralization of authority, commercialization, weakening of public education, and inadequate attention to social justice and inclusion. Issues such as multiple exit options, digital divide, and ideological influences in curriculum design are also examined.

The study concludes that while NEP 2020 introduces significant reforms, it must be assessed through the lens of equity, democratic values, and inclusivity. A balanced approach is necessary to ensure that education remains a public good that promotes critical thinking, social justice, and holistic development.

Introduction:

Education is one of the most fundamental processes through which human societies preserve, transmit, and transform knowledge across generations. Human beings possess the ability of consciously think, conceptualize, and reshape their environment. This ability is connected with the social production and collective experience. Therefore, education is not merely transfer the skills but generate the knowledge into the society and cultivate the ideologies, believes for the welfare of community.

The education system in India shifted Gurukul system to modern digital classroom. But the social discrimination has been changed its position. Over time, the role of education has evolved, particularly with the emergence of class-based societies. The basic ideological battle is not ended ever; but changed its shape. The dominant ruling class attempts to shape the consciousness of society. In this context, the National Education Policy (NEP 2020) must be examined not just as an educational reform but as a socio-political document reflecting broader economic and ideological shifts in India.

Education and Ideology:

The primary function of education is related to a means of survival, focusing on basic skill transmission in every age. It helps to mobilize the caste system. The caste system was based on the work system where the skills have been transferred. However, with the development of class divisions, education assumed a dual role. It continued to impart skills while simultaneously shaping the worldview of individuals according to the needs of the ruling class. In Marxist thought, ideology is seen as a set of false beliefs created by the ruling class. These false beliefs distort reality and prevent people from seeing the truth about exploitation and inequality.

Education became a powerful tool for maintaining social order. The dominant class, which controls material production, also influences intellectual production. The educational systems often reinforce existing hierarchies by promoting ideas that justify and sustain the normality. So, education acts as an instrument of ideology and transfer into the consciousness of working class people to set good atmosphere for ruling class.

Contradictions of Education under Capitalism:

The education has been spread with the rise of capitalism in worldwide. The new skills developed which were assist to increase production of industry. This skill based education established new society which move towards capitalist education. The require knowledge and skills set by industrialist with the help of rulings. On the other hand, it also creates awareness and critical thinking, which can challenge the very system it supports. Thus, education becomes both a tool of control and a potential instrument of resistance.

The systems of specialized fields are noted down in capitalist education which creates

fragmentation of knowledge such as natural sciences to social sciences. As a result the holistic development of student was restricted to understand the whole society and also obscures the relationship between labor, capital, and power.

Historical Development of Education in India:

The development of Education is traces out from ancient India where teaching done in the Gurukul system, where students lived with their teachers and received knowledge and skills; but this system allowed only to privileged caste person particularly to upper caste people. During the medieval period, education was influenced by religion, as a result Pathshalas and Tols (for Hindus) and Madrasas (for Muslims) focuses on the language skills and other religious activites. This system has been limited to religious and elite sections of society.

The Macaulay's Minute (1835) was promoting Western education in India. The major transformation happen during the colonial India where the caste and gender barrier has been blurred, but indirectly their education only focus on administrative and economic purposes. Introduction of English as a official language is simply goaled on class of educated Indians who helps them in governance. Apart from this, the education opened the gate of nationalist movement with deliberation. The political consciousness arises.

After independence, India aimed to democratize education. The Constitution emphasized free and compulsory education and recognized the importance of social justice. Policies were designed to expand access and address inequalities based on caste, class, gender, and region. Despite these efforts, significant gaps persisted.

The private-public investment in education remained inadequate, and access

continued to be uneven. Education increasingly became a privilege rather than a universal right.

Impact of Globalization and Neoliberal Policies:

In Liberalization era (after 1990), the privatization enters in the education system, as a result the motto of education for all has been gradually blurs. These changes had a deep impact on education. The state gradually reduced its role in providing education, opening the sector to private investment. Education began to be viewed as a market commodity rather than a public good. This led to the growth of private institutions, self-financing colleges, and foreign collaborations. It creates new barriers to the marginalized people who still are not connected to the mainstream. The quality education is only a matter of those who have economic capacity. The main purpose of education is now become institutions more profitable rather than inclusiveness of all.

The emphasis shifted towards technical and professional education, often at the expense of social sciences and humanities. This imbalance challenges the broader objective of education, which is to develop critical thinking and social awareness.

NEP 2020: Vision and Concerns:

The New Education Policy (NEP 2020) was approved on 29 July 2020 by the Union Cabinet of India. The National Policy on Education 1986 was replaced by NEP-2020. In the initial phase, the focus was on restructuring the education system, including the introduction of the 5+3+3+4 curriculum framework, promotion of mother-tongue instruction, and expansion of digital learning.

The National Education Policy 2020 presents itself as a transformative framework aimed at modernizing India's education system. It emphasizes flexibility, multidisciplinary learning,

and skill development. However, several concerns arise regarding its approach and implementation. The policy does not provide sufficient data or evidence to justify its recommendations. It appears more as a vision statement than a rigorously researched framework.

The centralization of power is shifted. NEP 2020 proposes significant centralization in decision-making. Institutions like the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) are expected to replace existing bodies, concentrating authority at the national level. This undermines the federal structure and reduces the autonomy of states and educational institutions.

The NEP 2020 gives the space to privatization and commercialization. The policy encourages private participation and financial autonomy, which may lead to increased commercialization. This raises concerns about affordability and equitable access, particularly for disadvantaged groups.

The introduction of multiple exit options in education is presented as flexibility. However, it risks legitimizing dropout rates, especially among economically weaker students who may be forced to leave education prematurely. This policy could not discuss the reason why student could not complete education, and they need to give students multiple exit and entrance.

The policy does not adequately address issues of reservation, affirmative action, and inclusion. This omission is significant given the historical inequalities in Indian society.

NEP 2020 challenges to public funded education. It provides space to privatization and reduction public fund particularly in rural and marginalized areas. The shift towards online education further impairs inequalities, as many students lack access to digital resources. This digital divide extremely affects disadvantaged communities.

One of the most debated aspects of NEP 2020 is its emphasis on cultural and historical narratives. The policy promotes the idea of inspiring pride in India's past through Indian Knowledge System (IKS) and integrating traditional skills systems through SEC Skill Enhancement Courses (SEC) into education. While this can be made a positive attitude to preserve cultural heritage, concerns arise when it leads to selective or distorted representations of history. There is a risk of promoting a singular narrative, because India has cultural diversity and pluralism. So, one India, one tradition could not be imposed through education. As consequences, the historical textbooks are rewrite and reinterpret for establishing ideological base through the NEP 2020. Such changes can influence how future generations understand society, culture, and identity.

Federalism and Institutional Autonomy:

Federalism is incorporated in the concurrent list of Indian Constitution part XI (11) defines the power distribution between the federal government (the Centre) and the States in India. The centralizing tendencies of NEP 2020 raise serious questions about federalism. Education, which was historically a state subject, is increasingly controlled by central authorities.

This shift reduces the ability of states to address local needs and contexts. It also limits the participation of academic communities in decision-making processes. Institutional autonomy of State Universities which is essential for innovation and academic freedom is also at risk. The emphasis on regulatory frameworks and centralized control may control independent thought and research of the institution.

Conclusion:

Education is not merely a technical process but a deeply political and social

institution. It shapes the consciousness of individuals and influences the direction of society. The National Education Policy 2020 represents a significant shift in India's educational landscape. While it introduces several innovative ideas, it also raises critical concerns regarding equity, accessibility, autonomy, and ideological orientation.

A truly effective education policy must prioritize inclusivity, scientific temper, and democratic values. It should ensure that education remains a public good accessible to all, rather than a privilege determined by economic and social status. The future of India's education system depends on addressing these challenges and fostering a framework that balances innovation with equity, and tradition with critical inquiry.

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